

NATIONAL EVOLUTIONARY SYNTHESIS CENTER

YEAR 5 ANNUAL REPORT

OCTOBER, 2009

NESCENT ANNUAL REPORT YEAR 5

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I. SUMMARY OF NESCENT ACTIVITIES IN YEAR 5

In the final year of funding of its inaugural grant, NESCent has consolidated its position as a major international Center for the study of synthetic evolutionary biology. Highlights of activities during year 5 include the following.

- We have conducted another successful year of applications and reviews. Activities undertaken at NESCent span a wide range of topics, covering the breadth of evolutionary biology and related disciplines; most are highly interdisciplinary. Many of the projects funded in earlier years have reach fruition and have resulted in high impact publications.
- We have expanded our postdoctoral training and professional development programs. Many postdoctoral fellows at the Center have moved into tenure track faculty positions; others have accepted further postdoctoral training opportunities. We continue to have an active in house community of scientists.
- NESCent's informatics program continues to be a world leader in evo-informatics. It has successfully supported the informatics needs of sponsored science, it has engaged in a variety of activities to promote standards for evolutionary data and software and it has taken the lead in a number of valuable cyberinfrastructure initiatives. The Dryad initiative is continuing to mature, and several prominent journals are poised to enter as full partners.
- NESCent continues to offer a range of training opportunities, from the well regarded evo-informatics courses, to the remote internships sponsored by Google and other organizations, to teacher training in evolutionary biology.
- Our education and outreach group has continued activities that bind together a wide range of educators and scientist to product material and construct approaches to make evolutionary biology more accessible to students and the public. We participated in a large number of local, national and international events commemorating the 200th Anniversary of Darwin's birth.
- We have partnered with a number of organizations to increase the participation of minority students in evolutionary biology, with particular emphasis on bringing more students to the annual Evolution meeting, and also providing a range of programs at the SACNAS meeting.
- With the hiring of a full time communications manager, NESCent's goal of developing a program to effectively communicate the results of NESCent science, as well as cutting edge evolutionary biology in general, has made a huge leap forward. We have developed a highly successful series of press releases, we have developed programs to communicate via a number of new technologies, and we have forged new links to scientific journalists and the blogging community.
- Throughout the current year we have worked to position ourselves for the next 5 years. A new Director and Associate Director of Science have been recruited. We have pursued new space for our ever expanding programs, and we have modified and developed new governance and oversight boards.

II. NESCENT SCIENCE AND SYNTHESIS

Synthetic research in evolutionary biology occurs along a continuum in terms of the scope of the scientific questions, tools and disciplines that may be involved. At one end of the continuum, synthesis involves integrating available data and models to address important problems within a discipline. Such research is essential for quantitatively evaluating the current state of a field, revealing important general patterns and results, and identifying critical gaps and promising directions for future research. At the other end, methods and perspectives from multiple disciplines are combined to develop new tools for answering-- and creating new-- fundamental scientific questions. NESCent's strategy for Science and Synthesis is to develop and support a portfolio of scientific activities that spans this spectrum of synthetic research in evolutionary biology and related fields.

Towards achieving this scientific portfolio, Science and Synthesis at NESCent has focused on five major goals during the past year: a) to maintain effective and open application and review processes; b) to attract and support a diverse and high-quality portfolio of research projects; c) to establish a vibrant and collegial in-house research community; d) to develop new scientific initiatives that broaden NESCent's reach and scope; e) to assess and ensure the productivity and impact of NESCent scientific activities. As summarized below, we have achieved or made significant progress on each of these goals during the past year.

APPLICATION AND REVIEW PROCESSES

Our on-line application, review and Board evaluation systems have been updated and these systems are now fully integrated with NESCent's more comprehensive administrative database. We have established a regular schedule for applications, with deadlines of 10 July and 1 December each year for working groups, catalysis meetings, and sabbatical scholars (1 Dec only for postdoc applications). The guidelines for proposals, criteria for evaluation, conflict of interest policies and informatics policies, are all available on our web site.

In the fall of 2009 the Senior Advisory Board and Science Advisory Board were merged into a single board. The NESCent Advisory Board is now composed of approximately 20 members, and maintains the excellence and diversity of the Board in terms of field, rank, gender and background (see current membership at http://www.nescent.org/dir/advisory_board.php). We are currently considering additional members for the Board, as current members continue to rotate off at the end of their 3-year terms. Details on the structure of this board are discussed in Section V, NESCent Administration.

SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITIES SUPPORTED BY THE CENTER

The two application deadlines in year 5 attracted 64 proposals and resulted in 24 awards (see Table 1 for summary). (Each proposal was ranked as Hi Priority, Fund if Funds Available, or Do Not Fund by the NESCent Advisory Board.)

Table 1. Science applications, year 5

	High Priority	FIFA	Do Not Fund	Total	Offered	Accepted
Catalysis Meetings	3	3	0	6	3	3
Working Groups	7	8	1	16	7	7
Postdoctoral Fellows	11	12	5	28	11	6
Long-term Sabbaticals	4	2	2	8	4	3
Short-term Visitors	5	0	1	6	5	5
Total	30	25	9	64	30	24

The complete listing of NESCent scientific projects funded in year 5 is given in Appendix 1. Collectively, they address a diversity of fundamental evolutionary questions in evolution, systematics and comparative biology. Table 2 summarizes the NESCent awards in year 5 in terms of subject areas (each proposal is classified as being associated with two or three scientific subject areas).

Table 2. Science awards, Subject areas: year 5 only

	Area 1	Area 2	Area 3	Total
Applied Evolution	0	1	2	3
Behavior or Neurobiology	2	0	2	4
Comparative Biology	6	6	0	12
Development	1	1	0	2
Education	2	0	0	2
Evolutionary Ecology or Population Biology	3	5	1	9
Genomics or Proteomics	1	0	0	1
Molecular Evolution	1	1	2	4
Other	2	1	0	3
Paleontology	1	0	2	3
Phylogeography or Speciation	1	2	2	5
Physiology or Functional Morphology	1	1	1	3
Population or Evolutionary Genetics	2	3	2	7
Systematics or Phylogenetics	1	3	3	7
Total	24	24	17	65

Table 3 summarizes the cumulative NESCent awards in years 1-5 in terms of subject areas. This summary demonstrates that our scientific research portfolio includes a wide range of approaches and biological levels of organization within evolutionary biology and associated fields.

Table 3. Science awards, Subject areas: yrs 1-5

	Area 1	Area 2	Area 3	Total
Applied Evolution	2	2	4	8
Behavior or Neurobiology	2	1	2	5
Comparative Biology	8	8	2	18
Development	1	2	1	4
Education	2	1	1	4
Evolutionary Ecology or Population Biology	10	10	6	26
Genomics or Proteomics	2	3	0	5
Molecular Evolution	4	1	2	7
Other	7	7	3	17
Paleontology	3	2	3	8
Phylogeography or Speciation	3	4	3	10
Physiology or Functional Morphology	4	2	1	7
Population or Evolutionary Genetics	6	8	5	19
Systematics or Phylogenetics	7	9	5	21
Total	61	61	37	159

THE NESCENT IN-HOUSE COMMUNITY AND POSTDOCTORAL DEVELOPMENT

We have maintained a vibrant and collegial community of in-house scientists. During year 5 the Center has had 17 postdoctoral fellows, 5 sabbatical scholars, 2 Triangle research fellows, 10 short-term visitors, and several visiting and resident scientists (Appendix 4). This community has a regular seminar series, a professional development series for postdocs, a journal club and several reading groups, active intranet communications, a Darwin Day scientific symposium, and a variety of social traditions.

NESCent has continually worked to improve the mentoring and professional development program for our postdocs. Recent improvements include an initial meeting for each entering postdoc with a mentoring committee to discuss the postdoc's research plans, NESCent expectations, local and other resources; and the development of a written mentoring plan for each postdoc.

Additionally, we have expanded our postdoc professional development series. Improvements in this process are due to the joint efforts of the NESCent Directors, the Assistant Director of Science, and the Education and Outreach staff. In 2009 major activities included

- a two-day NESCent Post-doc Retreat. This retreat included a half-day workshop on "Effective College Teaching" (new activity).
- multiple Postdoc Professional Development series throughout the year, including recent sessions on "Responsible Conduct of Research" (new topic), "Communicating Your Science to the Public," and "Writing a Teaching Philosophy Statement" (Appendix 9c).
- NESCent staff continue to provide ad-hoc, individual consulting and advising for NESCent postdocs on teaching and guest lectures, preparing teaching statements,

developing outreach and broader impact activities, manuscript review, etc. (throughout 2009).

SCIENCE ACTIVITIES AT THE CENTER

We supported 46 scientific meetings during the past year involving more than 800 visitors to NESCent (Table 4). In addition we hosted 5 meetings and 57 visitors by a variety of groups involved in evolutionary synthesis not supported by NESCent funds. A complete list of meetings at NESCent in year 5 is given in Appendix 2.

Table 4: Meetings and Visitors in Various Activities 1-5

Year	Science	Education	Informatics	Advisory	Hosted	Total	w/o Hosted
YR 1 Visitors	85	15	0	28	138	266	128
YR 1 Meetings	4	2	0	3	4	13	9
YR 2 Visitors	288	13	16	37	174	528	354
YR 2 Meetings	14	1	1	3	5	24	19
YR 3 Visitors	452	98	62	23	218	853	635
YR 3 Meetings	29	5	2	2	10	48	38
YR 4 Visitors	384	107	29	63	80	663	583
YR 4 Meetings	23	4	1	3	6	37	31
YR 5 Visitors	440	108	234	28	57	867	810
YR 5 Meetings	28	6	9	3	5	51	46
YR 1-5 Visitors	1649	341	341	179	667	3177	2510
YR 1-5 Meetings	98	18	13	14	30	173	143

PRODUCTS

The productivity of NESCent science projects has increased dramatically in the past year (Table 5). More than 200 publications have been reported from NESCent science activities to date. In year 5, 74 publications are reported as in review, in press, or published (Appendix 10). Postdoctoral fellows have been particularly adept at establishing new collaborations, and Catalysis meetings, as expected, have produced a significant number of new proposals and grants.

NESCent postdocs have been very successful in moving into faculty and other academic positions (Appendix 5), with 8 out of 15 postdocs completing their fellowships receiving tenure track positions.

Table 5: Products from NESCent Science Projects, Cumulative Through October 2009

	Postdoc	Sabbatical	Working Group	Catalysis Meetings	Other	Total
Publications	79	49	75	7	37	247
Proposals & Grants	5	4	11	12	19	51
Software & Datasets	13	0	16	0	10	39
Courses	1	0	0	3	0	4
Collaborations	26	4	4	10	19	63
News coverage	21	2	1	0	9	33
Other Products	29	2	14	8	15	68
Presentations	11	0	11	0	11	33

NESCENT SCIENCE IN YEAR 5: SOME HIGHLIGHTS

Results from working groups:

Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations using cohort data

PI(s): Diddahally Govindaraju (Boston University), Andrew Clark (Cornell University), Trudy Mackay (North Carolina State University at Raleigh), Stephen Stearns (Yale University)

This working group originated as a NESCent catalysis meeting in 2007. As a follow-up to that meeting, a subset of the participants formed a group to measure evolutionary change in modern human populations. They are beginning to publish their results, with their first paper appearing in the October 26th issue of [Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences](#). This paper takes advantage of data collected as part of a 60-year study of more than 2000 North American women in the Framingham Heart Study. The researchers analyzed a handful of traits important to human health. By measuring the effects of these traits on the number of children the women had over their lifetime, the researchers were able to estimate the strength of selection and make short-term predictions about how each trait might evolve in the future.

Having completed their first analyses of the women in the Framingham Study, the researchers are also preparing a companion paper on the men. Their findings have received widespread media attention, with articles in TIME, The Boston Globe, The Washington Post, Science Magazine, New Scientist, NPR's Science Friday, Radio New Zealand, and Discovery Channel Canada.

Phanerozoic body size trends in time and space: macroevolution and macroecology

PI(s): Jonathan Payne (Stanford University), Jennifer Stempien (University of Colorado at Boulder), Michal Kowalewski (Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State Univ)

This working group brought together paleobiologists as well as biologists studying modern organisms to explore how and why body size has changed over time. The group was extremely productive and resulted in several presentations and publications, including a high profile paper in [Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences \(PNAS\)](#). The paper, "Two-phase increase in the maximum size of life over 3.5 billion years reflects biological innovation and environmental

opportunity,” demonstrated two large increases in maximum size that correspond to the evolution of eukaryotic cells and multicellular organisms. The paper also revealed a striking correlation between the timing of these biological changes and increases in the level of atmospheric oxygen. They are preparing additional papers that will build on these findings.

In addition, the group has built a public database that covers a wide range of taxa across the Phanerozoic period. The database is publicly available and continues to grow. They have developed educational materials to help teachers and students use their data in the classroom, and are also producing an educational audio/video podcast that will feature group members talking about both the process and outcome of their work.

Relaxed selection and trait loss in evolution

PI: David Lahti (Queens College)

This working group produced a review paper which was selected as the cover for the September 2009 issue of *Trends in Ecology and Evolution (TREE)*. Titled "Relaxed selection in the wild," the review examines what happens when a significant source of natural selection is relaxed or removed, particularly why some traits decay quickly while others persist.

II. Results from postdoctoral fellows:

NESCent postdoc Carlos Botero published a paper in the May 21st 2009 issue of the journal *Current Biology* that received a fair amount of attention from both the science community and the press. Titled "Climatic patterns predict the elaboration of song displays in mockingbirds," the paper reveals that species in more variable climates also sing more complex songs. Botero's results have been featured in Science Magazine, BBC News, USA Today, ScienceNews, the Daily Telegraph, and the Financial Times.

NESCent postdoc Stephen Smith published a paper in the September 23rd issue of *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* examining how flowering plants adapted to new climates over the course of their evolution. By integrating previously published genealogies for several plant groups with temperature and rainfall data for each species, the study measures how fast each lineage filled new climate niches over time. Smith's analysis of more than 5000 flowering plant species reveals that woody plants such as trees and shrubs adapted to past climate change much more slowly than herbaceous plants did. Smith's work has been featured in the New York Times and in USA Today.

NESCent postdoc Eric Schuettpelz published a paper which appeared on the cover of *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (PNAS)*. In collaboration with Duke biologist Kathleen Pryer, Schuettpelz reconstructed the rise and early radiation of ferns. Their results were also featured in Science Magazine, and in the online science magazine Futurity.

III. Center wide activity

In 2007 a group of NESCent postdoctoral fellows and staff began a discussion on defining synthetic evolutionary biology. This resulted in a paper entitled "Linking Big: The Continuing Promise of Evolutionary Synthesis" (Brian Sidlauskas, Ganeshkumar Ganapathy, Einat Hazkani-Covo, Kristin P. Jenkins, Hilmar Lapp, Lauren W. McCall, Samantha Price, Ryan Scherle, Paula A. Spaeth, and David M. Kidd). This paper is now in press in *Evolution* as a commentary. It reviews the diverse approaches to synthetic evolutionary biology, and marks an interesting and creative collaboration among members of our in house community.

III. NESCENT INFORMATICS PROGRAMS

NESCent strives to bring a high level of informatics support to the wide variety of programs and activities in sponsored science, education, outreach, training and Center administration. Through its interactions with scientists, its software products, services and training activities, NESCent's informatics program a) facilitates scientific collaboration and synthesis, b) promotes standards for evolutionary data and software and c) engages the scientific community in the development of cyberinfrastructure.

FACILITATING SCIENTIFIC COLLABORATION AND SYNTHESIS

One way in which sponsored science projects are supported is through development of customized software products. These are often, but not exclusively, for collaborative data collection, storage, analysis and dissemination. Previous reports describe how such needs are peer reviewed and programming effort is allocated. This past year, major projects in which informatics staff members were involved included:

Evolutionary Ecology of Primate Life Histories. A database for the working group participants to organize and share data for their analysis: <http://plhdb.nescent.org>.

Phanerozoic Body Size Through Time and Space. A public web application that showcases the results of the working group for scientists and educators: <http://bodysize.nescent.org>.

Analysis and Synthesis of Physiologic Data from the Mammalian Feeding Apparatus: <http://feeding-dev.nescent.org/>. This database, currently still in development, will allow users to test hypotheses about the comparative biology of mammalian feeding using EMG, kinematic, and bone strain data for at least 36 mammalian species in 10 orders. Informatics staff assisted working group PIs with an NSF ABI grant proposal to further develop this as a community resource.

Evolutionary Shifts in Vertebrate Visual Ecology and Visual System Morphology: This past year, staff began development of a web-based collaborative data entry solution that encompasses features of both spreadsheets and databases (using Google Fusion), and a 'business intelligence' application for open-ended web-based data exploration (using Pentaho). The general tools being developed for this group can be adapted for other projects with similar data synthesis needs.

TreeTapper: <http://treetapper.org>: This uniquely valuable resource, a database of which phylogenetic comparative methods have been developed or implemented and which ones have yet to be developed or implemented, was the project of postdoctoral fellow Brian O'Meara. Informatics staff provided assistance in its development. The site is hosted at NESCent until O'Meara can transfer it to and maintained it at the University of Tennessee Knoxville.

In addition to these major projects, the informatics staff routinely assists resident scientists with cluster computing and other scientific computing needs. To anticipate future needs, staff have received training this past year in a number of relevant technologies, including use of the Open Science Grid, programming compute-intensive applications for graphics hardware (CUDA), applications for fast web database prototyping (Django, Ruby-on-Rails), and server virtualization. Many of these technologies have already been put to use. For example, NESCent now has a virtualized server infrastructure, which allows the Center to host web applications with a wider range of hardware, software and memory requirements.

Sponsored projects that do not require customized software products nonetheless frequently take advantage of the collaborative tools hosted by NESCent for all projects, including wikis, mailing lists and videoconferencing capabilities. This past year, we improved the training available in the use of wikis for all incoming working groups. The wiki ‘farm’ that we maintain makes it easy to host wikis as a community resource for partner initiatives, including EvoIO (described below), EvoS (at the University of Binghamton), HIVE (a project associated with the Dryad repository), and VertNet (www.vertnet.org). A dedicated videoconferencing room is being planned for the expansion space in the adjacent Grey Building, including high-fidelity audio and multiple fixed cameras; it will be operational early in 2010. The informatics staff continue to conduct entry and exit interviews of all resident scientists to assess their needs and inform them of the resources that are available, as well to make sure they are aware of NESCent policies (e.g. regarding the sharing of data and software).

PROMOTION OF STANDARDS FOR EVOLUTIONARY DATA AND SOFTWARE

NESCent, both through its sponsored science program, and through partnerships it develops with outside partners, works to promote the adoption of existing standards, and the development of new standards, in support of data reuse and synthesis. A number of activities in 2009 have been in support of this goal.

In 2007-2008 the Evolutionary Informatics working group developed a set of standards for the syntax, semantics, and exchange of evolutionary data (the so-called “EvoInfo stack”). For their fourth meeting, NESCent sponsored an Evolutionary Database Interoperability Hackathon from 9-13 March 2009 to implement these protocols within the context of a variety of different data resources and software tools. Of the invitees, 18 were invited and 5 applied through an open call. There has been a diversity of follow-up activities, including a Phylobase virtual mini-hackathon (focused on support for the aspects of the EvoInfo stack within R) and multiple Google Summer of Code projects (described below). In addition, a number of the participants from the working group and hackathon have since submitted a pending NSF INTEROP proposal (http://evoinfo.nescent.org/NSF_Interop_Proposal) to further develop the EvoInfo stack.

NESCent is an institutional member in the Biodiversity Information Standards organization (TDWG), and is active in promoting evolutionary data standards within this context. A new TDWG Interest Group on Phylogenetics Standards, which was officially approved by the organization in 2009, is co-organized by Hilmar Lapp (<http://www.tdwg.org/activities/phylogenetics/>). NESCent is also sponsoring a Phyloinformatics “Vocabulary Camp” to be held in conjunction with the 2009 TDWG Conference in November in Montpellier, France (<http://evoio.org/wiki/VoCamp1>).

ENGAGING THE COMMUNITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CYBERINFRASTRUCTURE

The informatics program also serves to reach beyond the Center as a voice for the interests and potential contributions of the evolutionary biology community in larger cyberinfrastructure initiatives.

Dryad

NESCent continues to lead development of the Dryad digital repository for the preservation and reuse of the data underlying publications. This is funded in large part through a separate grant

from NSF (DBI-0743720). The repository is now live at <http://datadryad.org>. Contents are now available under the terms of Creative Commons Zero (<http://creativecommons.org/choose/zero>). A web submission system was launched early in 2009 and currently, the data submission workflow is being integrated with the publication workflow of partner journals. Authors will receive a customized link upon acceptance of their article and authors need only upload their files to a pre-existing record that contains the basic data about the article. Dryad has begun collaborating with the developers of MetaCat (at the LTER Network Office) and TreeBASE to enable reciprocal harvesting and exchange of metadata holdings among repositories through implementation of the OAI-PMH standard. A data curation interface is also in development. The Dryad source code is now in a publicly accessible repository at Google Code (<http://dryad.googlecode.com>). This past year, NESCent Dryad staff began collaborating with information and library scientists at UNC Chapel Hill on an IMLS-funded project titled "HIVE (Helping Interdisciplinary Vocabulary Engineering)," which is benefiting Dryad by providing a uniform source for the controlled vocabularies needed for metadata within Dryad.

The first official meeting of the Dryad Management Board was held in May 2009 and included representatives from 17 different journals in ecology, evolution, and related fields. The Board is developing a business plan for journal governance and repository sustainability, data submission and use policies. A second meeting is to be held at the British Library, London, in December 2009. Partner journals are independently negotiating adoption of a joint data archiving policy, in which data deposition will be required for publication; an editorial describing the policy is scheduled to appear in the first partner journals in early 2010. Through Dryad, NESCent is a partner in one of the first two DataNet projects to be funded, DataONE (Data Observation Network Earth; <http://dataone.org>), and the closely related Virtual Data Center INTEROP project, both led by William Michener (described also under Partnerships). In addition to regular participation in technical development, community engagement, and leadership activities on these projects, NESCent hosted a DataONE planning meeting in August 2009 and organized the Summer Cyberinfrastructure Internship projects.

Phenoscape

NESCent is serving as a link between the evolutionary biology and bio-ontology community through Phenoscape (<http://phenoscape.org>), an NSF-funded project (DBI-0641025) that grew out of a working group led by Paula Mabee and Monte Westerfield to integrate phenotype data from model organisms and systematics through the use of ontologies. NESCent is developing software resources such as the Phenex data curation tool and the OBD database, which are built upon open standards from the bio-ontology community, as well as the continually maintained taxonomic and anatomical ontologies themselves, which are available through the NCBO Bioportal. The large and valuable store of curated data is delivered through the Phenoscape Knowledgebase (<http://kb.phenoscape.org>), which was released in July 2009. NESCent has engaged the community in this project in multiple ways in the past year. Several dozen systematics and morphology experts help build the resources through data curation and ontology development, both through mailing lists and occasional face-to-face jamborees. Phenoscape co-organized two workshops (with NCBO and AmphibAnat) on ontologies for evolutionary biology at several conferences (in 2009, SICB in Boston, MA in January, ASIH in Portland, OR in July). Personnel frequently consult with other ontology and phenotype informatics efforts (e.g. AmphibAnat, TraitNet). In 2009, Phenoscape brought two international student interns to NESCent (Sandrine Terceire from France, and Mtakai Ngara from Kenya). NESCent, with funding from Phenoscape and other sources, hosted an Evolutionary Ontologies Coordination workshop 27-28 April 2009 that brought together 19 current and potential future

developers and users of ontologies from many different areas of evolutionary biology (e.g. systematics, behavior, anatomy, developmental genetics, paleontology) to discuss common needs and coordinate efforts. The result was two proposals. The first is a pending NSF Research Coordination Network (RCN) proposal. The second is an ABI proposal that involves the Phenoscape PIs together with a broader set of collaborators (including Judy Blake, Suzi Lewis, Anne Maglia, Paul Sereno, and Peter Vize), that aims to push the state-of-the-art for computation with phenotype data in several new directions (e.g. inclusion of developmental stages and geologic time, enabling fast similarity search over complex phenotypes), and would extend the PhenoscapeKB to include data from across the vertebrates (including model organism data from zebrafish, mouse and Xenopus).

GMOD

GMOD is a network of software developers that maintains a suite of interoperable open-source tools for the management of genomic data (http://gmod.org/wiki/Main_Page). NESCent hosts a GMOD Help Desk through funding from NIH to coordinate end-user support for this large project. In this capacity, NESCent helps to glue the network together and also works to make developers aware of and focused on user needs. The GMOD Help Desk has done two formal surveys of users in 2009 (one general, one focused on genome browsers), organized two GMOD project meetings (at the PAG Meeting in San Diego in January, and at Oxford, UK in August), ran a workshop on "Database tools for evolutionary genomics" at SMBE in June, and gave presentations on GMOD at numerous conferences this past year. Many of these presentations have, by request, covered the use of GMOD tools to manage next-gen sequencing data, for which there is fast-growing demand; the Help Desk plays an important role in allowing the GMOD project to respond to such emerging user needs. The Help Desk is also responsible for the detailed extensive and well-maintained documentation available on the GMOD wiki, including step-by-step tutorials for using many of the most popular GMOD components.

TreeBASE 2

In 2009, in partnership with the recently concluded CIPRES project, NESCent took responsibility for hosting TreeBASE 2, the second generation of the popular [database for published phylogenetic trees](#), for up to five years. Software and data are being migrated from the San Diego Supercomputing Center to NESCent, and the database is being ported to an open-source platform so that it will be more portable in the future. CIPRES staff members continue to work on the code that will allow TreeBASE 2 to be publicly released in late 2009 or early 2010; it is already open for Beta testing by frequent data providers. Hosting TreeBASE 2 at NESCent will facilitate the goal of integrating the data submission process with that of Dryad, and will ensure that the user community maintains an active role in directing the future of this valuable resource.

INFORMATICS TRAINING

NESCent provides expert training in the skills of synthetic science. Training activities include both courses and a variety of internships, the latter funded mostly by non-core funds.

The Center is building a roster of classes that can be offered in rotation among years, and that can be occasionally offered at international venues (through partnership with other hosting institutions). In 2009, the course offerings included the following:

A new course on statistical meta-analysis was offered at NESCent, taught by 3 instructors (Jessica Gurevitch, Kerrie Mengersen, and NESCent postdoctoral fellow Marc Lajeunesse) to 24 students.

A Computational Phyloinformatics course held at the Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciência in Oeiras, Portugal from July 9-20, taught by 4 instructors (Darin London, Hilmar Lapp, Rutger Vos and William Piel) for 16 students. This was a Perl-centric version of the course that has been offered at NESCent for the previous two summers. The course had minority sponsorship from NESCent.

GMOD Summer Schools were offered both at NESCent and in Oxford, England in July and August, respectively (http://gmod.org/wiki/GMOD_Summer_School). The Summer School is a 4-day course with multiple instructors focused on software tools for managing genomic databases, such as GBrowse, Apollo, Chado, and Maker. The instructional materials from these courses have been made available as free online tutorials through the GMOD website. The courses were externally funded (from NIH and other sources).

NESCent also provides support for external courses and workshops, including the 2009 Analytic Paleobiology course at NCEAS (http://www.paleodb.org/cgi-bin/bridge.pl?user=Guest&action=displayPage&page=workshop_2010) and the Bodega Bay phylogenetics workshop (<http://bodegaphylo.wikispot.org>).

For the third summer in a row, NESCent has offered student internships with the aim of expanding participation in collaborative open-source software development projects. Students (and in some cases postdocs) from around the world apply to work remotely on a project largely of their own choosing, each under the guidance of an experienced mentor. This summer, NESCent received funding for 13 students; nine from the Google Summer of Code™ (GSoC) program, and four from the NSF Virtual Data Center (VDC) project (DBI-0753138).

2009 GSoC projects:

GPU acceleration for phylogenetic inference using OpenCL. Student: Daniel Ayres (graduate student, University of Maryland), Mentors: Aaron Darling (UC Davis), Marc Suchard (UCLA)

Biogeographical Phylogenetics for BioPython. Student: Nick Matzke (graduate student, UC Berkeley), Mentors: Stephen Smith (NESCent), Brad Chapman (Massachusetts General Hospital), David Kidd (Imperial College, London)

Biopython support for parsing and writing phyloXML. Student: Eric Talevich (graduate student, U. of Georgia), Mentors: Brad Chapman (Mass. General Hospital), Christian Zmasek (Burnham Institute for Medical Research, La Jolla CA)

Implementing phyloXML support in BioRuby. Student: Diana Jaunzeikare (undergraduate, Smith College), Mentors: Christian Zmasek (Burnham Institute, CA), Pjotr Prins (Wageningen University, Netherlands), Naohisa Goto (Osaka U., Japan).

BioPerl integration of the NeXML exchange standard and Bio::Phylo toolkit. Student: Chase Miller, Mentors: Mark Jensen (Fortinbras Research), Rutger Vos (U. of British Columbia)

Mapping the Bio++ Phylogenetics toolkit to R/BioConductor and BioJAVA using BioLib. Student: Adam Smith (graduate student, U. of Wisconsin), Mentors: Pjotr Prins (Wageningen U.), Chris Fields (U. of Illinois)

A BioLib mapping for the libsequence population genetic libraries. Student: Xin Shuai (graduate student, Indiana U.), Mentors: Chris Fields (U. of Illinois), Mark A. Jensen (Fortinbras Research), and Pjotr Prins (Wageningen U.)

Build a Mesquite package to view Phenex-generated Nexml files. Student: Kasia Hayden (undergraduate, Bennington College), Mentors: Peter Midford (U. of Kansas), Jim Balhoff (NESCent)

Enhancing the searching functionality of Phylr. Student: Dazhi Jiao (graduate student, Indiana U.), Mentors: Ryan Scherle (NESCent), Lucie Chan (San Diego Supercomputing Center)

2009 VDC Summer Cyberinfrastructure Internship projects

Generating accurate vocabulary term ranking algorithms via machine learning. Student: Christine Dumoulin (graduate student, Northwestern U.), Mentors: Mentor(s): Bruce Wilson (Oak Ridge Nat. Lab.), Dave Vieglais (U. of Kansas), Giri Palanisamy (ORNL)

Vocabulary Term Mapping. Student: Namrata Lele (graduate student, Indiana University), Mentors: Dave Vieglais (U. Kansas), Bruce Wilson (ORNL)

Refactoring the EarthGrid SOAP API to REST style and an implementation for Metacat. Student: Serhan Akin (graduate student, Istanbul Technical University), Mentors: Matt Jones (NCEAS), Mark Servilla (LTER Network Office)

Semantic phyloinformatic web services using the EvoInfo stack. Student: John Harney (graduate student, U. of Georgia), Mentors: Hilmar Lapp (NESCent), Rutger Vos (U. British Columbia)

More details on the program and projects are available from <http://bit.ly/1pm8OE> and <http://bit.ly/1dUYGz>.

IT SUPPORT FOR CENTER ADMINISTRATION, EDUCATION, AND OUTREACH

This past year, NESCent's administrative database (NEAD) reached operational maturity. While improvements continue to be made, NEAD is now able to satisfy a large portion of the Center's reporting requirements (e.g. data on participants, activities, products, etc.). In addition, NEAD is being used to directly provide much of the data on NESCent's public website. Through close integration of staff from across the Center, procedures for ensuring data quality and completeness have been put in place and are undergoing regular evaluation.

SELECT COLLABORATIONS AND PARTNERSHIPS IN 2009

CIPRES. The TreeBASE 2 database was migrated to NESCent from the San Diego Supercomputing Center. It is being ported to an open-source database backend and prepared for public release in late 2009.

Dublin Core Metadata Initiative. Dryad personnel helped to launch the Dublin Core Science and Metadata community (<http://dublincore.org/groups/sam>), a forum for individuals and organizations to exchange information and knowledge about metadata describing scientific data.

iPlant. Informatics staff attended the iPlant-sponsored Cyberinfrastructure Meeting at Biosphere2 in January 2009. NESCent is cosponsoring the fourth meeting of the Plant Evogenomics Working Group together with iPlant in Phoenix in November 2009.

DataONE. NESCent (through Dryad) and NCEAS are partners in one of the two recently announced NSF DataNet projects. Other partners include a wide variety of repositories, libraries and data centers, all with a focus on the long-term preservation of data in ecology, environmental science, and evolutionary biology (<http://dataone.org>).

GMOD. In 2009, NESCent continued to host the Help Desk for the GMOD project and promote adoption of GMOD standards and tools within emerging genomic model organism communities, through funds from NIH.

Google. NESCent was again a mentoring organization for the Google Summer of Code.

NIMBioS. Informatics staff participated in the "Training the trainers" course in high-performance, parallel and grid computing.

Society for Systematic Biology. NESCent will be sponsoring a satellite informatics conference (tentatively titled ePhylo) to be held in conjunction with the 2010 Evolution Meetings, with SSB serving as a society host. Lapp is on the organizing committee and substantial planning has already begun.

TDWG. Participation in the TDWG Interest Group on Phylogenetics Standards, as described above, and sponsoring of a Phyloinformatics VoCamp at the 2009 TDWG conference.

TraitNet RCN. Hilmar Lapp will participate in the TraitNet Ontology Development workshop, also being held to coincide with the TDWG Conference in November.

IV. EDUCATION AND OUTREACH AT NESCENT

The Education and Outreach Group at NESCent has continued to sharpen its focus on key areas of our mission: improving evolution education and public understanding of evolutionary science, and communicating current and emerging evolution research. We have worked to develop effective programs, to build collaborations, to expand on established resources, and to take advantage of NESCent's scientific expertise.

A significant expansion of our outreach and communications capabilities was achieved through hiring a full time Communications Manager, Dr. Robin Smith, in May 2009. Smith has a Ph.D. in evolutionary biology, and has worked as a freelance science writer. Her responsibilities include writing the results of NESCent science for both general and specialist audiences, and coordinating with NESCent sponsored scientists to have results broadly distributed (Appendix 9b). Smith is also a major contributor in planning and content development for the NESCent webpage and re-designed newsletter (www.nescent.org/news/Newsletter_NESCent.php) and for the newly launched NESCent web news aggregator site, Kaboodle (kaboodle.nescent.org). Since Smith's arrival there has been a marked increase in traffic to our website (Appendix 9a).

We continue to add to our portfolio of products that utilize various electronic media to disseminate evolutionary biology research and promote education. These include video capture of presentations, a podcast program based on the *Evolution in the News* series, and interviews with NESCent scientists, educators, and visitors. An exciting element of our endeavors this year was coordinating Center-wide and community-based activities to celebrate the bicentennial of Charles Darwin and sesquicentennial of *The Origin of Species*.

NESCent continues its broad array of connections across disciplines, academic, and research institutions to strengthen and expand our contributions to shared community goals through national initiatives that work to improve biology education, disseminate cutting edge research findings, and expand the public understanding of science.

We work closely with sponsored scientists, working groups, and catalysis meetings to develop broader impacts and disseminate findings. Education and outreach staff supported and participated in two education-focused working groups: Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education (TREE) and Evolution Across the Curriculum (EVAC); and we hosted a meeting of Education and Outreach groups from the other NSF Synthesis Centers, the iPlant Collaborative, NEON, and the Encyclopedia of Life.. Our education and outreach Program Manager, Dr. Jory Weintraub, and Program Consultant, Dr. Kristin Jenkins work across these activities to contribute expertise, connect NESCent participating scientists and postdocs with outreach and education initiatives, and to promote NESCent science and projects to the public, academic, and research communities.

Across all of these activities, NESCent works to provide opportunities that expand participation of minorities and minority serving institutions in evolutionary biology, provide a multi-faceted program of professional development opportunities and events for Center postdocs, and contribute in the planning, conduct and development of NESCent short courses and workshops.

IMPROVING EVOLUTION EDUCATION AND PUBLIC UNDERSTANDING OF EVOLUTIONARY SCIENCE

Evolution in the News

NESCent continued a strong collaboration with the University of California's Museum of Paleontology's Understanding Evolution (UE) through the *Evolution in the News* program. The *Evolution in the News* program provides a clear explanation of the evolutionary concepts behind stories found in the popular media. In addition to the text explanation, the program includes an audio/video podcast interview with a scientific expert on the topic, additional readings, classroom activities and discussion questions.

Along with UE, we produced eight *Evolution in the News* podcasts in 2009 (www.nescent.org/eog/postcasts.php):

- “Tough Conservation Choices? Ask Evolution!” (Dec. 08)
- “Happy 200th, Darwin!” (Feb. 09)
- “Sex, Speciation and Fishy Physics” (March 09)
- “Better Biofuels through Evolution” (April 09)
- “Coping with Climate Change” (May 09)
- “A Species’ Unwelcome Inheritance: Extinction Risk” (Sept. 09)
- “Where Did All of Madagascar’s Species Come From?” (Oct. 09)
- “Chemistry of Evolution” (Nov. 09)

As part of this collaboration, we received an NSF CCLI type 1 grant to evaluate and improve the accessibility and effectiveness of the *Evolution in the News* program. As part of this assessment we are surveying students and instructors about their experience with the materials. A graduate student with the UNC Evaluation, Assessment and Policy group is managing the field test surveys, and is supervised by a faculty member in that program. A preliminary pilot test of survey materials was conducted in Spring 2009, and over 30 field testers across the country have volunteered for Fall 2009. We will continue producing monthly stories and podcasts, and apply the information from the surveys to improve the program over the next year.

“Year of Darwin” 2009

In celebration of the “Year of Darwin” 2009, we co-organized and hosted a diverse array of activities to bring attention to Darwin’s contributions and to highlight the relevance and impact of evolutionary theory in everyday life, applied biological research, and diverse areas of human knowledge and culture.

We organized and hosted our annual Darwin Day Symposium at the Sigma Xi headquarters in Research Triangle Park, NC. The theme this year was ‘Darwin’s Legacy: Evolutionary Approaches to World Challenges’. Five distinguished speakers were featured: Fred Gould (NCSU), Barbara Schaal (Washington U.), Dan Faith (Australian Mus.), Katia Koelle (Duke), and Steven Benner (FfAME). The symposium was written up in the Journal Science Blog series, Origins <http://blogs.sciencemag.org/origins/2009/02/nescent-symposium-covers-appli.html> (Feb. 09).

We produced a video series entitled “Tea with Darwin” (https://www.nescent.org/news/Darwins_Birthday.php#tea) in which NESCent scientists were invited to chat with Darwin over tea, to pose questions, remark on his accomplishments and raise issues brought to light in the 150 years since *The Origin*.

We collaborated with the NC Museum of Natural Sciences (NCSMNS) and the NCSU Keck Center for Behavioral Biology on a public lecture series in celebration of the Year of Darwin. These are evening lectures held in the NCMNS Theater and the videos are posted on our website (<http://www.nescent.org/news/speakers.php>). Lectures have been very well attended with enthusiastic and interesting audience question and answer sessions following each speaker. The speakers included: Carl Zimmer (Independent Science writer) - "Darwin and Beyond: How Evolution Is Evolving" (Feb. 09); Rob Dunn (NCSU) - "Life After Darwin: Are There Still Big Discoveries to be Made in Biology?" (March 09); Anne Yoder (Duke University) - "Madagascar's Magnificent Biodiversity: What Would Darwin Say?" (July 09); Dale Russell (NCMNS) - "Islands in the Cosmos: The Evolution of Life on Land" (Oct. 09); Paul Brinkman (NCMNS) - "Charles Darwin's Beagle Voyage and the Origin of 'The Origin'" (Nov. 09).

Among our other Year of Darwin events, we are co-hosting with WUNC Public Television, “Re:Design,” a dramatization of scientific correspondence between Charles Darwin and botanist Asa Gray, presented at NCSU. We provided images, scientific support and organized a panel of researchers for post-play discussion (Nov. 09). We operated an information booth about NESCent sponsored programs at Darwin Day, University of Wisconsin (Feb. 09) and collaborated with COPUS on the February Year of Science website (Feb. 09). EOG is leading the planning for Darwin Day 2010 (Sept. 09).

NABT Conference and Evolution Symposium

NESCent continued an ongoing collaboration with AIBS to organize and deliver a symposium on evolutionary biology at the annual conference of the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT). At this year’s conference (Denver CO, Nov 2009), we featured a half-day symposium entitled “Evolution in Extreme Environments.” In addition to the symposium, NESCent, AIBS and UE offered a half-day, hands-on workshop for teachers to provide them with tools and resources for teaching the concepts presented in the evolution symposium. In addition to playing a major role in planning, organizing and designing the symposium and teacher workshop, we developed a multimedia CD of educational resources for the symposium. At this meeting we also participated in sessions related to the EVAC working group, and staffed a NESCent informational exhibit booth.

Education Working Groups

NESCent has continued its involvement in several evolution education-related working groups. Our staff are active participants and play important leadership and planning roles in the working group’s activities.

- Evolution Across the Curriculum (EVAC) working group meeting: This was the third meeting of EVAC. Eight group participants attended. This group worked toward developing and disseminating exemplars for EVAC modules. Further development will occur in conjunction with UE through an NSF funded CCLI phase 2 grant. The group launched its e₂biology initiative – to develop an online introductory biology curriculum using an evolutionary theme. (May 09).
- TREE (Tree Reasoning in Evolution Education) working group meeting: This

was the third and final meeting of the TREE working group. Nine working group participants attended. The goals were to synthesize scholarly efforts to characterize student's understanding of phylogenetics, develop a conceptual framework for describing and assessing understanding across areas of tree reasoning, and promote the development and use of curricular and instructional strategies that emphasize tree reasoning across biology instruction. Work during the meeting focused on three projects: Developing a "field guide" to phylogenetic trees (a brief primer for teachers), planning for preparation of a review manuscript (a "State of the Field") summarizing what is currently known about tree-thinking, and discussions of developing/assembling a collection of curriculum pieces to help teach trees. It was agreed that work on all of these projects would continue in small groups beyond this final meeting. (Sept. 09)

- **Synthesis Centers Coordination Meeting - Education, Outreach and Communication Staff:** This was the first meeting of this group, which consists of Education, Outreach and Communications staff from a variety of NSF-funded research centers and projects (as well as AIBS and EoL/BioSynC). A total of 14 EOC staff, as well as two program officers from the NSF attended this two-day meeting, which was planned/organized and hosted by NESCent. The goals of the meeting were to begin building a community of center EOC staff, familiarize ourselves with the EOC work being done by the other centers, exchange information about successes and challenges, explore potential collaborations, and define/discuss a shared vision for education, outreach and communication at the centers. Outcomes included strengthened commitments to continue and expand collaborations (such as the CCLI Resource Center proposal which is being developed) and an agreement to continue to meet as a group on an annual basis (with a different center hosting the meeting each year). (Oct. 09)

Development, implementation of workshops and courses

NESCent Teacher Workshop - We organized and delivered a three-day workshop for high school teachers on effective teaching of evolution. This workshop featured lectures and classroom exercises designed to expand and update evolutionary biology course content. NESCent scientists, EO staff and postdocs contributed lectures and course material. (15 course participants) (June 09)

In conjunction with the SSE Education Committee, EO staff developed a one-day teacher workshop preceding the Evolution 2009 conference. The "Evolution 101 Teacher Workshop" was attended by about 35 K-16 educators and Evolution conference attendees. The presentation on biogeography was originally developed by members of the NESCent working group "[Developing an Integrative Algorithmic Method for Historical Biogeography](#)" and was lead by Kathryn Perez, a member of that group (June 09).

NESCent EO staff participated in the following conferences to present information about NESCent programs and NESCent educational initiatives and materials: Wisconsin Society of Science Teachers (March 09); University of Wisconsin Evolution Initiative (March 09); UNC Morehead Planetarium and Science Center teacher workshop (April 09); National Science Teachers Association annual meeting in Minneapolis, MN (Oct. 09); North Carolina Science Teachers Association annual meeting in Greensboro, NC (Nov. 09).

Understanding Evolution (Univ. of California Museum of Paleontology):

Brian Wiegmann (Associate Director) and Kristin Jenkins (Project Consultant) serve on the Understanding Evolution Advisory Board of the Understanding Evolution program at UC Berkeley. Both attended the annual UE board meeting and grant writing session (Dec. 08). NESCent is collaborating with UE on both phase 1 and phase 2 CCLI grants.

COMMUNICATING CURRENT AND EMERGING EVOLUTION RESEARCH (BOTH WITHIN AND BEYOND NESCENT) AND PROMOTING NESCENT

Led by new Communications Manager, Robin Smith, NESCent works to promote and disseminate information on NESCent sponsored research, meetings, and projects (Appendix 9b). These activities include development of press releases, interaction with NESCent postdocs, working groups, sabbatical scholars, and catalysis meetings, as well as participation in national and local professional societies for science communicators, and national projects designed to enhance public understanding of science.

In addition we initiated a number of activities in traditional and non-traditional media to increase the presence of NESCent in the press, internet and blogosphere. These included redesign and upgrading of the NESCent newsletter; initiating a travel award contest for ScienceOnline 2010: Evolution Blogging meeting to be held in Raleigh NC (Jan 2010); introducing a NESCent Twitter feed, a NESCent Wikipedia page (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Evolutionary_Synthesis_Center), and a new news aggregator site, Kaboodle (<http://kaboodle.nescent.org/>). Revision of our website is underway. In the past year we have experienced close to a doubling of website traffic.

EXPANDING OPPORTUNITIES IN EVOLUTION FOR UNDERREPRESENTED GROUPS

NESCent has continued a variety of general programs to increase the opportunities for underrepresented groups in evolutionary biology. In 2009 we organized and administered a travel award program for faculty at Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs) to attend the SMBE conference in Iowa City, IA. Three faculty members (from Virginia State University, Tuskegee University and City University of New York) attended the conference and participated in a symposium on “Teaching Molecular Evolution.” (June 09).

For the second consecutive year, NESCent collaborated with Drs. Scott Edwards and Rich Kliman on the “Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution” travel award program. This program sends up to 25 undergraduate students (including several from underrepresented groups) to the annual Evolution Societies (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference, provides on-site mentoring and professional development workshops, coordinates a poster session at which the students present their own research and arranges social functions. In addition to providing logistical, organizational and financial support, several NESCent postdocs served as mentors for the undergraduate students. (June 09)

NESCent organized and administered travel awards for eight students from underrepresented groups participating in NESCent Meta-Analysis Summer Course. (July 09)

Once again, NESCent planned, organized and implemented a suite of activities focusing on evolution and ecology at the annual SACNAS (Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science) Conference. These activities included a career mentoring session,

scientific symposium, field trip and “Movie Night” event. Events were co-sponsored by NCEAS, AIBS, ESA and SSE, with financial support from NSF and Springer.

NESCent staff arranged and coordinated a visit by Dr. Toby Kellogg (NSF Program Officer) to UNC Pembroke (an historically Native American university) and accompanied her on visit as representative of NESCent (Dec. 08)

SELECT LIST OF EOG COLLABORATIONS AND PARTNERSHIPS IN 2009

University of California Museum of Paleontology – NESCent collaborates with the *Understanding Evolution* website (based within UCMP) on the *Evolution in the News* project. Drs. Wiegmann and Jenkins also serve on the UE advisory board. NESCent is also a partner for the *Undergraduate Library* extension of *Understanding Evolution*.

UNC Evaluation, Assessment and Policy (EvAP) Group – NESCent is working with EvAP on a CCLI-funded assessment project to evaluate the effectiveness of the *Evolution in the News* project.

North Carolina Museum of Natural Sciences – NESCent collaborated with NCMNS on this year’s “Darwin Speaker Series” as part of the *Year of Darwin* activities, and will be collaborating on future Darwin Day activities, as well.

Keck Center for Behavioral Biology (NCSSU) – The Keck Center was a co-sponsor of the “Darwin Speaker Series.”

WUNC TV, NC State University Theater Department – As part of the *Year of Darwin* activities, NESCent is collaborating with these groups to sponsor the staging of a theatrical production entitled “Re: Design,” a dramatization of scientific correspondence between Charles Darwin and Asa Gray.

Coalition on the Public Understanding of Science (COPUS) – NESCent collaborated with COPUS on their February “Year of Science” website, which focused on evolution.

Center EOC Groups – The Education/Outreach/Communication groups from NESCent, NCEAS, NIMBios, iPlant, NEON, EoL/BioSynC and AIBS established a partnership this year that will involve annual meetings in the future to build/expand collaborations, share resources, etc.

American Institute of Biological Sciences (AIBS) – NESCent and AIBS collaborate to put together the annual NABT Evolution Symposium. AIBS also contributes to the sponsorship and organization of NESCent’s SACNAS activities, and participates in the Center Education, Outreach and Communication working group.

National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) – NESCent and AIBS work with NABT to offer the annual Evolution Symposium at the NABT conference. NESCent is also involved in the newly formed “Outreach Coordinator” section of NABT.

Society for the Study of Evolution (SSE) – NESCent is a sponsor of the annual Evolution Societies (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference, co-sponsors the “Diversity at Evolution” travel award and mentoring program and collaborates on SSE Education Committee-sponsored teacher workshops at the Evolution meeting and NABT conference each year. Dr. Jenkins is a member of the SSE Education Committee.

Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Rich Kliman (Cedar Crest College) – NESCent co-sponsors the “Diversity at Evolution” travel award and mentoring program with Drs. Edwards and Kliman each year, contributing organizational and logistical support, mentors for undergraduates, and funds to the program.

Society for the Advancement of Chicanos and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS) – NESCent organizes a suite of outreach activities focusing on evolution and ecology at the SACNAS conference each year, with the support and collaboration of the SACNAS leadership and conference organizing committee.

NCEAS/ESA/SSE/AIBS/NEON – These organizations co-sponsor NESCent’s annual SACNAS outreach activities.

Springer (Evolution: Education and Outreach) – Drs. Jenkins and Weintraub are members of the editorial board of the journal *Evolution: Education and Outreach*. Dr. Jenkins also served as a guest editor of the September 2009 issue. Springer provides financial support of NESCent’s outreach activities at the SACNAS conference each year.

ScienceOnline – NESCent is a sponsor of the annual ScienceOnline science blogging conference. In 2010, NESCent participates in an evolution blogging travel award contest to send evolution bloggers to the conference which will be held in January in Research Triangle Park, NC.

Science Communicators of North Carolina (SCONC) – NESCent Education/Outreach/Communications staff are active members of SCONC, and in November of 2009 NESCent will host a monthly SCONC meeting, at which several of NESCent’s postdocs will present their research to SCONC members.

BioQUEST – NESCent and BioQUEST collaborate on several projects, including problem space development, workshops, and posting BioQUEST developed materials on the DryEd project.

V. NESCENT ASSESSMENT ACTIVITIES

NESCent has begun to develop a multi-faceted assessment program. With the completion of NEAD, our administrative database, we have in place a mechanism to assess routine aspects of proposals, demographics and participation in Center activities. In the coming years we will undertake a summative assessment of the results of NESCent funded activities. However, we have placed high priority on putting into place our formative assessment of activities in year 5. This project, titled the Science of Science program, is now well underway.

SCIENCE OF SCIENCE PROJECT

In January of this year, NESCent began the “Science of Science” portion of our self-evaluation program (Tier 3). This portion of our assessment is based on formative analysis (i.e., developmental and on-going such that the results can be used to actively improve the ways that the Center promotes synthetic evolutionary biology). The focus of the assessment will be on the behaviors and attitudes of scientists towards collaboration, and how such behavior is changed as a result of NESCent funding. The project results will provide NESCent with important information about the value of its programs in building communities and in creating a culture of collaboration.

In order to conduct such assessments, we are collaborating with Professor Jonathon Cummings (Associate Professor of Management) from the Fuqua School of Business at Duke University, assisted by Chris Shields as a full time assessment coordinator.

We are focusing on four programs through which participants produce knowledge and build relationships at NESCent and beyond: (1) working groups, (2) catalysis meetings, (3) post-doc and sabbatical visits, and (4) informatics hackathons. We will use observations, interviews, and surveys to provide feedback on the effectiveness of these programs within NESCent.

At NESCent since January 2009, there have been four catalysis meetings, one hackathon and 17 working group meetings. Of these, the “Science of Science” project has evaluated one catalysis meeting (25% of total), one hackathon (100%) and 7 working groups (41%). The capability for NESCent to perform these evaluations has increased with the arrival of Chris Shields given his full time presence at NESCent as well as his primary focus on evaluation. Since he arrived September 1, all six working groups that have met at NESCent have been included in the assessment. As the assessment program continues we fully expect to increase the percentage of meetings included in our analyses.

The “Science of Science” program is beginning to see some preliminary results for the informatics hackathon and working group analyses. Catalysis meetings are less frequent; therefore there are no preliminary results at this time. The interviews of post-doctoral and sabbatical scholars are in the final stages of preparation and have just begun. When looking at preliminary trends from working group survey analyses, we see attendees citing more theoretical and synthetic approaches to questions in their NESCent work compared with their other work. The preliminary survey results also suggest that more disciplines are involved in working group collaborations than in previous and non-NESCent collaborations. Further, comments suggest that participants in NESCent collaborations are moving towards broader and more integrative outlets than in previous collaborations. Finally, fewer graduate students are involved in working group collaborations when compared to previous collaborations. This last result has further encouraged our activities to increase the participation of graduate students in working groups.

Using network visualizations of the March 2009 hackathon participants, we highlight how the density of collaborations has increased as a result of the hackathon. In examining the data, we see that the subgroups formed during the hackathon had a strong impact on collaboration. These subgroups included the Taxonomic Intelligence, Java API Library to NeXML, Phylr, and Visualization subgroups. We are currently following up six months later to see which network ties persist, and what factors may predict these persistent ties (e.g. database use, tool use, language use, and resource use).

VI. NESCENT ADMINISTRATION IN YEAR 5

During year 5 considerable time was spent consolidating the administrative advances achieved in years 2-4, putting in place new staff and programs in response to previous years site visit comments; recruiting new leadership to the Center; and planning for and beginning programs for the renewal grant and years 6-10.

CONSOLIDATING ADMINISTRATIVE ADVANCEMENTS

A major administrative achievement has been the completion and curation of data in NEAD, NESCent's administrative database. Newly hired Assistant Director for Science, Craig McClain, provided excellent leadership in this process. This database now is used for registration of all activities and participants; it is integrated with the proposal submission system, and it is fully integrated with the products report system. Considerable time was spent on updating and ensuring the accuracy of legacy data. Although we anticipate continued upgrades and improvements, it should form the basis for a solid assessment and reporting process for the Center.

Continuing with our strong record of submitting and receiving Federal grants beyond the core for support of Center initiatives, we submitted a number of proposals, arising either out of ongoing programs or new initiatives. These grants are listed in section VII and include proposals both in informatics and education.

As NESCent has grown, both in our core and also our associated programs (e.g., Dryad), we have outgrown our current space. During year 5 significant effort was devoted to identifying new space and designing its renovation. This space will house a number of our informatics staff members and will also have a new state-of-the-art video and remote conferencing room. We are requesting that some carryover funds be applied to the renovation and equipping of this room.

STAFF AND LEADERSHIP CHANGES

In year 5 there were a number of staff additions. These included:

Dr. Craig McClain was hired as a new Assistant Director for Science. His portfolio includes oversight of NEAD, interaction with sponsored science activities, mentorship of postdocs, leadership in assessment activities, and working with the outreach program to ensure that the results of NESCent science have a high visibility to the scientific community and the public through a variety of avenues, including our website and general outreach.

Dr. Robin Smith was hired as new Communications Officer. Robin's portfolio includes working with NESCent scientists to ensure the results of their work received the highest possible attention, ensuring that NESCent has a presence in various electronic media and other outlets, helping NESCent scientists communicate their work, and interacting with science writers, bloggers, and broader community.

Chris Shields was hired as a new Assessment coordinator. Chris' primary responsibility is in the Science of Science program, but he will also be working with others at NESCent to develop Tier 2 assessment protocols.

Lori Slack was hired as an accounting specialist. This was necessary as the Center's activities grew in size and complexity. A chart of current staff and anticipated hires is shown in Appendix 11.

CENTER LEADERSHIP

In 2009, in anticipation of the departures of Kathleen Smith and Joel Kingsolver, a new Center Director and Associate Director for Science were hired.

Dr. Allen Rodrigo will assume the role as NESCent Director in February 2010. He was recruited from the University of Auckland in New Zealand, and will be a Professor of Biology at Duke University.

Dr. Susan Alberts, Professor of Biology at Duke University, will serve as Associate Director of Science, starting in December 2009, with the beginning of the new grant.

GOVERNING BOARD MODIFICATIONS

As part of our evaluations of Center function during the preparation of a renewal proposal in 2008, we proposed that the two NESCent advisory boards be merged into one. Further a more explicit process of Center evaluation and oversight by the participating Universities was developed. Two new Boards will be constituted at the beginning of the renewal. During year 5 considerable effort was exerted to define the most appropriate process. The roles, composition and processes of these boards may be briefly summarized.

NESCent Advisory Board

The NESCent Advisory Board provides advice on the scientific merit of proposals to NESCent as well as on the Center's science, informatics and educational initiatives and programs; it is the link between the Center and the wider scientific community. The members of the NESCent Advisory Board will represent the diversity of evolutionary biology and NESCent's broad constituencies. A Chair and Vice Chair will be selected from among the current membership of the Board. The Chair will chair the meetings of the group (except for proposal review, which will be chaired by the Associate Director for Science and Synthesis), will oversee the writing of a brief summary of major recommendations of the Board, and will lead the nomination for his/her successor. Both the Chair and Vice Chair will serve as members of the Oversight Committee.

NESCent Oversight Committee

The Oversight Committee provides independent evaluations of the Director, and the Associate Directors, and oversight of the Center's strategic and financial plans. It also provides an independent forum for conflict resolution. It will be composed of a senior representative (such as a Senior Associate Dean or higher) from each participating institution, and the Chair and Vice Chair of the NESCent Advisory Board. The institutional representatives will be appointed by the Vice Provost for Research at Duke University, after consultation with individuals from the host institution. The Vice Provost from Duke University serves as an ex officio member of the Committee. The Chair will be appointed by the Vice Provost for Research at Duke University. The Committee reports to the Provost of Duke University through the Vice Provost for Research, and will provide a summary of its evaluation of NESCent Directors annually to the NSF.

THE RENEWAL GRANT: NESCENT LOOKING FORWARD

Perhaps our most important activity in year 5, which spanned all branches of the Center, was in positioning the Center to move forward into years 6-10 with energy, imagination and impact. A brief summary of our expectations for years 6-10 is below.

1) Establish a new call for proposals for targeted major initiatives. One of the strongest consensuses to come out of the Community Summit was the notion that NESCent fund major initiatives that might have large impact on societal issues (applied evolution, conservation, etc.), might span broad disciplines (biological and social sciences) or might produce technologies of major impact (visualization). Funding of activities spanning multiple aspects of NESCent is likely to have larger impact. Further this initiative will balance the competing suggestions that NESCent take more initiative in setting funding directions while ensuring our science is largely community driven.

2) “Catalyze catalysis.” One of our most innovative and successful programs is our “catalysis meeting” in which groups that are highly interdisciplinary or very broad are brought together to define new areas of research communality. We will begin to target a few of these, working with our advisory group to identify areas that might benefit from the NESCent experience and inviting/encouraging certain individuals or groups of individuals to apply. In particular we may use this venue to bring areas from outside of evolutionary biology into evolutionary biology. Areas that have been suggested include areas such as metagenomics, phenotype/genotype studies, microbial evolution; areas that are not core evolutionary biology such as neurobiology, or areas of applied evolution.

3) Graduate fellowships. NESCent has not, thus far, targeted any program towards graduate students. In the future we will provide a number of graduate fellowships that are primarily linked to working groups. We feel it is best to link the graduate fellowships to projects that are already funded, as we are not in a position to mentor students ourselves. The students on these fellowships will be encouraged to spend part of their fellowship at NESCent, and part working on the project of the working group in their home labs. It is expected that the students be full members of the group throughout its lifetime.

4) Expansion of support to working groups. We will expand our support to working groups to up to \$10,000 and we will routinely support a 4th meeting of each group.

5) Greater emphasis on coordinated submission of proposal types. We will actively advertise, recruit and fund coordinated efforts among working groups, postdoctoral and sabbatical fellows.

6) Increase training efforts. We will expand our very valuable training programs in informatics, and will begin to accept a number of community initiated training efforts. These latter efforts will be solicited as regular proposals and reviewed by our Advisory Board.

7) Expand community initiated programs in EOG. We will actively recruit and fund proposals for sabbaticals, postdocs and working groups in the areas of science outreach and communication, citizen science, science pedagogy and education.

VII. NESCENT EXTERNAL FUNDING

FUNDED

DataONE: Observation Network for Earth

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: W. Michener)

National Science Foundation (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Direct: \$390,490; NESCent Total Amount: \$501,780

8/1/2009 – 7/31/2014

A Digital Repository for Preservation and Sharing of Data Underlying Published Works in Evolutionary Biology

National Science Foundation, BD&I (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Direct: \$1,907,531; NESCent Total Amount: \$2,180,169

9/1/2008 – 8/31/2012

Show Me the Evolution! Assessing Effectiveness of a New Teaching Resource

National Science Foundation, CCLI (PI: Kathleen Smith)

Total Direct Costs: \$117,976; Total Amount: \$150,000

1/1/2009 – 12/31/2010

INTEROP: International Virtual Data Center for the Biodiversity, Ecological and Environmental Sciences

Subaward through University of New Mexico (PI: William Michener)

National Science Foundation (PIs: Kathleen Smith and Hilmar Lapp)

NESCent Total Direct: \$39,535; NESCent Total Amount: \$50,803

7/15/2008 – 6/30/2012

Helping Interdisciplinary Vocabulary Engineering (HIVE)

Subagreement through UNC – Chapel Hill ((PI: J. Greenberg)

Institute for Museum and Library Sciences (PI: Kathleen Smith)

NESCent Total Amount: cost share only to Duke University

1/1/2009 – 6/30/2011

Linking Evolution to Genomics Using Phenotype Ontologies

Subaward through University of South Dakota (PI: Paula Mabee)

National Science Foundation BDI-0641025 (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$853,338 NESCent Total Amount: \$1,050,945 (D&I to UNC)

6/1/2007 - 5/31/2010

Enhancement of the GBrowse Genome Annotation Browser

Subaward through University of California at Berkeley (PI: I. Holmes)

National Institutes of Health (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$242,565; NESCent Total Amount: \$310,482 (D&I to UNC)

9/1/2007 - 8/31/2010

Development of the www.EcoliCommunity.org Information Resource

Subaward through Texas A&M Research Foundation (PI: Jim Hu)

National Institute of General Medical Science (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$30,550; NESCent Total Amount: \$39,104 (D&I to UNC)

6/1/2007 – 5/31/2009

A Next Generation E. coli Model Organism Resource

Subaward through Texas A&M Research Foundation (PI: Jim Hu)

National Institute of General Medical Science (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$83,411; NESCent Total Amount: \$106,766 (D&I to UNC)

8/01/2009 – 7/31/2013

Extending and Enhancing Understanding Evolution for the Undergraduate Community

Subaward through the University of California - Berkeley (PI: Roy Caldwell)

National Science Foundation (PI: Brian Wiegmann)

NESCent Total Direct: \$22,809; NESCent Total Amount: Total: \$28,740 (D&I to NCSU)

9/1/2009-8/31/2012

TreeBASE2 Hosting and Database Migration

Contract agreement through Center for Computational Biology and Bioinformatics, University of Texas at Austin (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Amount: \$23,000 (Direct only)

4/13/2009-9/30/2009

IN REVIEW

Ontology-Enabled Synthesis of Gene-phenotype Data: A Hypothesis-Generating Knowledgebase for Systematics and Evo-Devo Applied to Fossil and Modern Vertebrates

Subawards through the University of South Dakota (PI: Paula Mabee)

National Science Foundation, ABI (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Duke Total Direct: \$ 529,161; NESCent Duke Total Amount: 646,841 (D&I to Duke)

NESCent UNC Total Direct: 589,849; NESCent UNC Total Amount: 750,996 (D&I to UNC)

6/1/1010 – 5/31/2014

Enhancing the GMOD Suite of Genome Annotation and Visualization Tools

Subaward through University of California at Berkeley (PI: I. Holmes)

National Institutes of Health (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$481,994; NESCent Total Amount: \$616,952 (D&I to UNC)

9/1/2010 - 8/31/2015

INTEROP - A Network for Enabling Community-Driven Standards to Link Evolution into the Global Web of Data (EvoIO)

Subaward through the University of Maryland Biotechnology Institute (PI: Arlin Stoltzfus)

National Science Foundation (PI: Todd Vision)

NESCent Total Direct: \$144,945; NESCent Total Amount: \$169,762

6/1/2010 – 5/31/2013

The Feeding Experiments End-user Database (FEED): An Open-Access Database for Integrated Evolutionary Analyses of Mammalian Feeding

National Science Foundation, ABI Collaborative Research (PI: Christine Wall)

Duke Total Direct: \$227,297; Duke Total Amount: \$333,918

8/01/2010 - 7/31/2013